

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

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SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION IN ATHEROSCLEROSIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS

For citation: Agababyan R. Irina, Ismoilov M. Rajabboy. Systemic inflammation in atherosclerosis on the background of chronic periodontitis. // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 2, pp. 166-172

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11300515>

ANNOTATION

Modern data show that in the most effective treatment of atherosclerosis and all diseases of the cardiovascular system, it is necessary to follow 3 basic principles of this disease. These are: control of dyslipidemia, control of hemostasis and control of the inflammatory response[29]. In recent years, attention has increased to colchicine as an anti-inflammatory agent not only in the treatment of gout, but also in the treatment of patients with myocardial infarction and chronic cardiovascular diseases. The anti-inflammatory effect of colchicine is associated with several mechanisms, the main of which is the reduction and elimination of the inflammatory process [30]. In order to increase the effectiveness of treatment for joint diseases and atherosclerosis, the administration of colchicine reduces and eliminates risk factors that can cause diseases.

Key words: coronary heart disease, myocardial infarction, atherosclerosis, C-reactive protein, colchicine.

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SURUNKALI PARODONTIT FONIDAGI ATEROSKLEROZDA TIZIMLI YALLIG'LANISH

ANNOTATSIYA

Hozirgi ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki ateroskleroz va yurak-qon tomir tizimining barcha kasalliklarini eng samarali davolashda, keltirilgan kasallikning 3 ta asosiy tamoiliga amal qilish shart hisoblanadi. Bular: dislipidemiyani nazorat qilish, gemostazni nazorat qilish va yallig'lanish reaksiyasini nazorat qilish[29]. So'nggi yillarda yallig'lanishga qarshi dori sifatida kolxitsinga e'tibor nafaqat podagrani davolashda, balki miokard infarkti va surunkali yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bilan og'rigan bemorlarni davolashda qullanish suratlari oshdi. Kolxitsinning yallig'lanishga qarshi ta'siri bir nechta mexanizmlar bilan bog'liq bo'lib, ularning asosiysi yallig'lanish jarayonini susaytirish va bartarab etish[30]. Qo'shma kasalliklar va ateroskleroz birga kelganda davolash samaradorligining

o'shinish maqsadida kolxitsinni kiritish kasalliklarni keltirib chiqarishi mumkin bulgan xavf omillarini kamaytiradi va bartaraf etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: parodontit, yurak ishemik kasalligi, miokard infarkti, ateroskleroz, C-reaktiv oqsil, kolxitsin.

Qisqartmalar: CRO- C-reaktiv oqsil, YuIK- yurak ishimik kasalligi, MI- miokard infarkti, YuQTK- yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, ysCRO- yuqori sezuvchanlik C-reaktiv oqsil, AYuQTK- Aterosklerotik yurak qon-tomir kasalliklari.

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СИСТЕМОЕ ВОСПАЛЕНИЕ ПРИ АТЕРОСКЛЕРОЗЕ НА ФОНЕ ХРОНИЧЕСКОГО ПАРОДОНТИТА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Современные данные показывают, что при наиболее эффективном лечении атеросклероза и всех заболеваний сердечно-сосудистой системы необходимо следовать 3 основным принципам указанного заболевания. Это: контроль дислипидемии, контроль гемостаза и контроль воспалительной реакции[29]. В последние годы возросло внимание к колхицину как противовоспалительному средству не только при лечении подагры, но и при лечении больных инфарктом миокарда и хроническими сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями[30]. Противовоспалительное действие колхицина связано с несколькими механизмами, основным из которых является уменьшение и ликвидация воспалительного процесса. С целью повышения эффективности лечения при заболеваниях суставов и атеросклерозе введение колхицина снижает и устраняет факторы риска, способные вызвать заболевания.

Ключевые слова: пародонтит, ишемическая болезнь сердца, инфаркт миокарда, атеросклероз, C-реактивный белок, колхицин.

Parodontit - yumshoq to'qimalar va tishlarning tayanch qismini surunkali infeksiyasion yallig'lanishi[31].Parodontitda surunkali yallig'lanish reaksiyasi ko'p hollarda asta-sekin rivojlanadigan va og'riqli alomatlarga olib kelmaydigan doimiy subgingival bakterial plaklardan kelib chiqadi [30,31].

Ateroskleroz - bu oksidlangan lipoproteyinlar va boshqa antigenlarga tizimli va mahalliy immunitet reaksiyasi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan lipidlar almashinuvining buzilishi fonida arterial devorga zarar etkazuvchi omillar bilan qo'zg'atilgan surunkali yallig'lanish jarayoni. Ateroskleroz eng muhim tibbiy-ijtimoiy muammolardan biri bo'lib, uning klinik ko'rinishlari kasallanish va o'lim ko'rsatkichlari tarkibida etakchi o'rinni egallaydi. Ateroskleroz - bu ko'p omilli kasallik bo'lib, u yirik arteriyalar devorlarida degenerativ o'zgarishlarning rivojlanishi, keyinchalik qon tomirlari o'tkazuvchanligining kamayib borishi va yurak, miya va buyraklar kabi muhim organlarga qon ta'minoti cheklanishi bilan tavsiflanadi. Subklinik (asimptomatik) ateroskleroz eng keng tarqalgan patologiya hisoblanadi; Arteriyalarning aterosklerotik zararlanishi allaqachon yoshlarda aniqlanmoqda va klinik ko'rinishlarning rivojlanishiga qadar o'nlab yillar davomida barqaror rivojlanadi. O'rta yoshda, aterosklerozning klinik ko'rinishi bo'lmagan shaxslarda, aterosklerotik tomirlar zararlanish aniqlash darajasi 100% ga yaqinlashadi [21].

Aterosklerozning patofiziologiyasi an'anaviy ravishda arterial devorlar yuzasida lipid to'planishining ko'payishi bilan izohlanadi, bu qon oqimining kamayishi yoki to'liq bloklanishiga olib keladi, bu miokard yoki miya infarkti kabi yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarini keltirib chiqaradi.Aterosklerozning rivojlanishida yallig'lanishning asosiy rol o'ynashi haqida dalillar ortib bormoqda. aterosklerozning barcha bosqichlarida, erta lezyonlarning shakllanishidan tromboemboliyagacha [5,19,20]. Yallig'lanish belgilarining, xususan, C-reaktiv oqsilning (CRO) yuqori darajalari ateroskleroz xavfining oshishi bilan bog'liq [16,17,18] va miokard infarktidan (MI)

omon qolganlarda koronar infarkt va o'lim xavfi ortadi. yurak ishimik kasalligi (YuIK) [14-15].⁹ Bu yallig'lanish xavfini kamaytirish yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari (YuQTK) bilan bog'liq natijalarni yaxshilashning ajralmas qismidir. Kanakinumab bilan trombozni yallig'lanishga qarshi davolashni o'rganish shuni ko'rsatdiki, CRO darajasi ≥ 2 mg/L dan yuqori bo'lgan O'MIdan omon qolganlarda interleykin-1 β ni to'g'ridan-to'g'ri inhibe qilish orqali uning yallig'lanishga ta'siri yurak-qon tomir tizimiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishning oddiy kamayishiga olib keldi. Biroq kanakinumab iqtisodiy jihatdan samarali davolash usuli emas va bu tadqiqotda sepsis va o'limga olib keladigan inyeksiya kabi jiddiy nojo'ya hodisalar haqida xabar berilgan [14]. YuQTK bilan kasallanishni kamaytiradigan yana bir yallig'lanishga qarshi dori bu podagrani davolashda keng qo'llaniladigan antitubulin preparati Kolxitsindir.

Kolxitsin - *Colchicum autumnale* o'simligidan olingan lipofil trisiklik alkaloidi (rasm). Bu Ebers papirusida osteoartikulyar og'riqlar uchun vosita sifatida eslatib o'tilgan qadimiy dori bo'lib, miloddan avvalgi 1500 yilga oid qo'lyozma. U asrlar davomida ma'lum bo'lgan va o'nlab yillar davomida yallig'lanishga qarshi vosita sifatida podagra xurujlarini, yaqinda oilaviy O'rta er dengizi isitmasi va yaqinda perikarditni davolashda ishlatilgan.

Ancient kingdom of Colchis

Colchicum autumnale

Colchicine

Rasm. *Colchicum autumnale* o'simligi va molekulyar tuzilishi

Kanakinumab tomonidan interleykin-1 β ni tanlab ingibir qilishdan farqli o'laroq, kolxitsin tubulin polimerizatsiyasini ingibir qilish va leykotsitlar sezgirligini o'zgartirishni o'z ichiga olgan keng hujayrali ta'sirga ega. [22.23.24].

Bemorlarda kolxitsinning yurak-qon tomir tizimiga tasir natijalarini (COLCOT) o'rganishga kirishdan oldin tekshiriluvchilarda 30 kun ichida miyokard infarkti, o'tkir og'ir darajali yurak-qon tomir yetishmovchiligi, insult yoki shoshilinch kasalxonaga yotqizilgan stenokardiyalarni hisobga olish kerak. Kuniga bir marta 0,5 mg kolxitsin olganlar orasida koronar revaskulyarizatsiya darajasi placebo qabul qilganlarga nisbatan pastroq bo'lgan. [25]. Surunkali koronar arteriya kasalligi bilan og'rigan bemorlarda past dozali kolxitsinni (LoDoCo) ilgari o'tkazilgan tadqiqotda biz shuni aniqladikki, kuniga bir marta 0,5 mg Kolxitsin qabul qilganlar orasida Kolxitsinni qabul qilmaganlarga qaraganda o'tkir yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfi pastroq bo'lgan. [26].

Kolxitsin kanakinumab bilan solishtirganda kengroq ta'sir mexanizmiga ega va tubulin polimerizatsiyasini inhibe qilishni o'z ichiga oladi, bu yallig'lanish yo'llarining bostirilishiga va leykotsitlar reaktivligining o'zgarishiga olib keladi [13]. Kolxitsin yuqori sezuvchanlik CRO (ysCRO) darajasini pasaytirishi aniq ko'rsatildi, bu kelajakda kuzatilishi mumkin bo'lgan yurak qon-tomir kasalliklarining rivojlanishini sezilarli darajada kamaytiruvchi belgidir. Bundan tashqari, surunkali yurak ishemik kasalligi bilan og'rigan bemorlarda kolxitsinning past dozasi (0,5 mg) bilan kuzatuv nazorat ostida o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlar natijalari shuni kursatdiki past dozada berilgan kolxitsin yurak qon-tomir kasalliklari natijasida kelib chiqadigan umumiy xavfini kamaytiradi. Biroq o'rganishlarda MI [10,11] dan o'limga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmadi. Nonspesifik yallig'lanishga qarshi davolovchi

metotreksatning shunga o'xshash tadqiqotlari shuni ko'rsatdiki, u yurak qon-tomir kasalliklari natijalariga ta'siridagi yallig'lanish belgilarini kamaytirmadi [9]. Binobarin, hozirgi vaqtda yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining ikkilamchi profilaktikasi uchun yallig'lanishga qarshi dori-darmonlarni muntazam ravishda qo'llashni tasdiqlovchi hech qanday dalil yo'q va shuning uchun ularni davom ettirishni oqlash mumkinmi yoke yo'qmi degan savol tug'iladi. Kolxitsinning ysCRO ga ta'siri isbotlangan bo'lsa-da, uning lipidlarga ta'siri aniq emas. Kolxitsinning qisqa muddatli (30 kun) ta'sirini o'rganish surunkali qon tomir kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarda lipidlar darajasiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmadi. Biroq, kemiruvchilarda o'tkazilgan tajribada giperlipidemiya ga kolxitsin bilan 5 haftalik davolash plazma lipidlarini kamaytirish uchun natija ko'rsatdi. Shuning uchun qo'shimcha klinik tadqiqotlarga ehtiyoj bor.

Neytrofillar odamlarda eng ko'p uchraydigan yallig'lanish hujayralari va tug'ma immunitet tizimida infeksiyaga qarshi birinchi himoya chizig'i hisoblanadi [5,6]. Ular suyak iligidagi gematopoetik ildiz hujayralarining (HSCs) miyeloid nasldan olingan. Patogenlar aniqlangandan so'ng, neytrofillar fagotsitoz va hujayra ichidagi degradatsiya, degranulyatsiya va neytrofil hujayradan tashqari tuzoqlarni hosil qilish orqali invaziv patogenlarni ushlaydi va yo'q qiladi [4,2]. Bundan tashqari, so'nggi o'n yillikda paydo bo'lgan dalillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, neytrofillar surunkali yallig'lanishda ishtirok etadi va surunkali yallig'lanish kasalliklari, jumladan periodontit, Aterosklerotik yurak qon-tomir kasalliklari (AYuQTK) va periodontit bir-biri bilan chambarchas bog'liq [3]. Xususan, neytrofillar sonining ko'payishi va periodontit tufayli giperreaktivlik AYuQTKning har qanday bosqichiga yordam berishi mumkin. Kelajakdagi tadqiqotlar ushbu gipotezani eksperimental ravishda sinab ko'rishi kerak. Biroq, taxmin qilish hali ham qiziq.

Periodontit tufayli kelib chiqqan neytrofillardagi o'zgarishlar bu tushunchani qo'llab-quvvatlovchi bir nechta klinik tadqiqotlar tufayli periodontit va AYuQTK o'rtasidagi bog'lanishga yordam beradi [32,33]. Periferik qonda neytrofillar sonining ko'payishi periodontit bilan og'rigan bemorlarda AYuQTK xavfini oshirishi mumkin, chunki periferik qondagi neytrofillar soni AYuQTK xavfi bilan ijobiy bog'liqdir [1,2].

4992 ishtirokchi ishtirok etgan 39 ta randomizatsiyalangan sinovlarning Kokronovskiyning tizimli tekshiruvini shuni ko'rsatdiki, kolxitsin barcha sabablarga ko'ra o'limga olib kelmaydi (RR 0,94, 95% CI 0,82-1,09), garchi tadqiqot yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bo'lgan bemorlarni ham, ularsiz ham ko'rib chiqdi. Biroq, Verma va boshqalar tomonidan yurak xastaligi bilan og'rigan 3431 bemorni tekshirgan meta-tahlilda kolxitsini birgalikda qo'llash yurak-qon tomir tizimida (RR 0,44, 95% CI 0,28 dan 0,69 gacha) umumiy o'lim darajasining pasayishi tendentsiyasini (HR 0,50, 95% CI 0,23 dan 1,08 gacha) natijalarining kamayishi bog'liqligi aniqlandi [28]. Yaqinda e'lon qilingan COLCOT tadqiqotida o'rtacha 20 oy davomida past dozali kolxitsini (kuniga 0,5 mg) yaqinda miokard infarkti bo'lgan 4745 bemor ishtirok etdi. Ushbu tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, kolxitsin yurak-qon tomir ishemik hodisalari (shu jumladan yurak-qon tomir o'limi, yurak tutilishi, miokard infarkti, insult yoki stenokardiya uchun shoshilinch kasalxonaga yotqizish) chastotasini kamaytirishi kuzatildi ularning kamayish nisbati quyidagicha bo'ldi: 7,1% ga nisbatan 5,5% (xavf darajasi 0,77, 95% interval 0,61 dan 0,96 gacha). Bu farq, asosan, insult yoki stenokardiya uchun shoshilinch kasalxonaga yotqizish hollari bilan bog'liq edi. Yon ta'sirlarning o'xshash tez-tezligiga qaramay, asosan oshqozon-ichak trakti (16% ga nisbatan 15,8%, $p = 0,89$), og'ir pnevmoniya kolxitsin bilan davolash paytida tez-tez uchraydi (0,9% ga nisbatan 0,4%, $p = 0,03$). Ushbu tadqiqotning kichik guruhlar tahlili kolxitsin va placebo o'rtasidagi yuqori sezuvchanlik C-reaktiv oqsil darajalarida unchalik katta bo'lmagan farqni ko'rsatdi [27]. Ushbu topilma O'KSda aniq yallig'lanish (mahalliy va tizimli) yo'llarning gipotezasini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

Kardiyovaskulyar holatlarning oldini olish uchun kolxitsinning optimal dozasi hozircha noma'lum. Yaqinda o'tkazilgan meta-tahlil shuni ko'rsatdiki, kolxitsinning past dozasi (kuniga 0,5 mg) bilan davolash kasalliklarining rivojlanishini sekinlashtirishini ko'rsatdi va shu bilan birga kolxitsinning kuniga 1 mg dan yuqori dozalarini qo'llashdagi qo'llab-quvvatlovchi dalillar mavjud emas [31]. Kolxitsin yurak-qon tomir tizimiga sezilarli darajada ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin, ammo tor terapevtik indeksga ega, ayniqsa keksalarda va buyrak yoki jigar funksiyasining pasayishi holatlarida va hatto hayot uchun xavfli toksiklik paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Shundan kelib chiqqan

holda, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarini davolashning ushbu arzon va istiqbolli usulining samaradorligi, dozasi va xavfsizligini yanada baholash uchun qo'shimcha keng ko'lamli tadqiqotlarga ehtiyoj bor [27].

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Статья поступила в редакцию 04.03.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 22.04.2024; принята к публикации 26.04.2024.

The article was submitted 04.03.2024; approved after reviewing 22.04.2024; accepted for publication 26.04.2024.

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Источники финансирования: Работа не получала какого-либо специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы заявляют об отсутствии явных или потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией этой статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Агабабян И.Р. — идеологическая концепция работы, написание текста; редактирование статьи;

Исмоилов Р.М. — сбор и анализ литературных источников, написание текста.

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Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Agababyan I.R — ideological concept of the work, writing the text; editing the article;

Ismoilov R.M. — collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

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9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

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JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

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